

OBSERVATIONAL SIGNATURES OF AGN FEEDBACK

DOMINIKA WYLEZALEK

NADIA ZAKAMSKA
JENNY GREENE
THAISA STORCHI-BERGMANN

ALLAN SCHNORR MÜLLER
ROGEMAR RIFFEL
MANGA TEAM

JOHNS HOPKINS
UNIVERSITY

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- 1. INTRODUCTION**
 - 2. EVIDENCE FOR AGN-DRIVEN OUTFLOWS**
 - 3. HOST GALAXY IMPACT**
 - 4. SYSTEMATIC OUTFLOW-GALAXY STUDIES
WITH SDSS-IV MANGA**

WHY AGN FEEDBACK?

Observations:

- relations between host galaxy bulge properties and black hole properties
- idea of BH/galaxy self-regulation

Simulations:

- Solve overcooling problem, lower baryon fraction in massive galaxies
- Reproduce LF, color-bimodality etc.

INTRODUCTION

Until recently:

- Few observations of quasar feedback

Earliest evidence:

- Radio jets, bubbles

Cattaneo+2009

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Earliest evidence:

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BUT:

- radio-loud AGN population only $\sim 10\%$
- most feedback in radio-quiet sources
- AGN driven winds/outflows?

Cattaneo+2009

INTEGRAL FIELD UNITS (IFU)

Spatially resolved:

- stellar/gas parameters
- stellar/gas kinematics

credit: S. Todd, D. Pierce-Price

The background image shows a galaxy with a bright, yellowish-white central region. Two prominent, blue, jet-like structures extend outwards from the center, one towards the top-right and one towards the bottom-left. The galaxy's disk is visible in shades of blue and purple, with some internal structure. The overall scene is set against a dark, starry background.

EVIDENCE FOR AGN-DRIVEN OUTFLOWS

IONIZED GAS OUTFLOWS I

- Preferred tracer: $[\text{OIII}]5007\text{\AA}$
- Galaxy-wide outflows with high velocity dispersions in luminous quasars
- Mass outflow rates:
10-1000 $M_{\text{sun}}/\text{year}$

Liu+2013a,b, Brusa+2015,
McElroy+2015, Carniarni+2016,
Kakkad 2016, Harrison+2016

extreme velocities

SDSS J0149-0048

high negative asymmetries

SDSS J0149-0048

QUASAR SCATTERING CONES

QUASAR HOST GALAXIES

Scattering cones aligned with outflow velocity field

Quasar host galaxies are bulge-dominated galaxies

High merger fraction

High star formation rates

Host Galaxy (HST optical)
Scattering Cone (HST UV)

Liu+2013a,b, **Wylezalek+2016a**, **Obied+2016**

IONIZED GAS OUTFLOWS II

Powerful red
quasars at $z \sim 2$
with FWHM \sim
3000-5000 km/s

Zakamska+2016

IMPACT ON HOST GALAXY?

LOCAL EVIDENCE

Cano-Diaz+2012, see also Cresci+2015, Carniarni+2016

IMPACT ON HOST GALAXY — NEED FOR LARGE SAMPLES

EVIDENCE FOR SUPPRESSION OF sSFR

- negative correlation between sSFR and velocity width at high SFRs
- coupling between wind+gas is potentially strongest
- relative signatures of AGN feedback

SYSTEMATIC OUTFLOW-GALAXY STUDIES WITH SDSS-IV MANGA

- WIND LAUNCHING
- WIND PROPAGATION
- IMPACT ON HOST

SDSS-IV MANGA: AN IFU SURVEY OF UNPRECEDENTED SIZE

- 10 000 galaxies by 2020
- Fibers in bundles - IFU
- $z \sim 0.03$
- Spatial resolution: 1.5-2''
- Spectral resolution: ~ 60 km/s

SDSS-IV MANGA: AN IFU SURVEY OF UNPRECEDENTED SIZE

- > 1000 AGN
- MaNGA ideal for large scale kinematics
- AGN are expected to be of intermediate luminosity: allows for systematic study of small scale vs. large scale wind kinematics

Zakamska+Greene 2014
see also Veilleux+2013

FEEDBACK THRESHOLD WITH MANGA/GMOS

FEEDBACK THRESHOLD WITH MANGA/GMOS

- Pilot Project: 2 sources**
- 1 bona-fide AGN
 - 1 AGN-candidate

- “Blob Source”:
Ambiguous AGN/BPT
signatures in galaxy center

FEEDBACK THRESHOLD WITH MANGA/GMOS

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Outflow Signature!

SYSTEMATIC OUTFLOW-GALAXY STUDIES WITH SDSS-IV MANGA

**Unbiased selection
+ large AGN sample:**

systematic analysis of outflows in relation

- to AGN properties
- to galaxy potential
- to environment

CLASSIFYING AGN IN IFU DATA IS DIFFICULT!

Effects “faking” AGN-like ionization signatures:

- Hot old stars (pAGB stars)
- Hot young stars (WR stars)
- Diffuse ionized gas (changes in ionization parameter)
- AGN-unrelated shocks

Increasingly important at large galactocentric distances!

Wylezalek+submitted

HOW MANY AGN HAVE WE BEEN MISSING?

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SUMMARY

- Ample evidence of AGN-driven outflows in low and high- z powerful quasars
- First evidence for AGN-driven outflows suppressing SF in galaxies
- MaNGA:
 - AGN selection in IFU surveys opens up new parameter space but comes with challenges
 - playground for AGN science, systematic analysis of small-scale to galaxy-wide feedback signatures in relation to host galaxy parameters